

Sri Ramakrishna's Pedagogy in the light of Upanishadic System of Teachings

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ABSTRACT : The educational institutions during the Upanishadic age were the preceptors' homes which were used to be as the Parishads, the debating circles and the conferences. In those Institutions both Para and Aparavidyas were taught. It was only after the completion of Aparavidya, the students would be eligible for Para Vidya. Since it purely dealt with the Philosophical knowledge, subtle and sophisticated methods of teaching abstract philosophy were in use. In the present study on Sri Ramakrishna's pedagogy it has been observed that Upanishadic system of teaching played havoc in resembling the pedagogy of Sri Ramakrishna and he even surpassed the Upanishads in his own capacity wherein lies his genius and uniqueness.

Keywords : Enigmatic, Aphoristic, Dhara Vidya, Udgitha Vidya, Madhu Vidya, soliloquy.

Introduction

Building the student's character was one of the aims of education during the age of the Upanishads. Character training, in fact, meant the training of the will which is a mental force. The will power must be strengthened and properly directed which is possible through the practice of concentration, self-control and culture of refined and lofty sentiments. The student's will power was strengthened and also directed towards good things alone while they lived in

the house of their preceptors. There, they had to live as Brahmacharins, who besides their daily duties, had to practise concentration, self-control and training of sentiments. The students had to live under the direct supervision of their preceptors who were held responsible not only for their intellectual progress but also for their psycho-physical behaviours. The severe rules which they had to follow in the preceptor's house were to develop their character in such a way that they could become pure in their ideas, words

and deeds. Their everyday life followed the etiquettes and good manners towards their elders, equals and juniors. They were trained to become well-adjusted members of the society and also to be gainfully employed in various works on completion of their education. During the period of studentship they were enjoined upon the following duties:

- i. Righteousness to be practised along with learning and teaching.
- ii. Truthfulness to be practised along with learning and teaching.
- iii. *Austerity to be practised along with learning and teaching* (Gambhirananda,1957).

Conferences, debates and discourses were held on various educational subjects. Questions and cross-questions were put by the pupils or the contending candidates and there used to be a judge or a board of judges to decide as to who among the scholars engaged, was victorious. Dialogues were also used to impart the Vedic knowledge. In addition to the debating competitions 'Not only the students, but the teachers who were eminent scholars and sages also launched on debating bouts with zeal and seriousness.'(Basu, 1969)

Upanishadic methods and Sri Ramakrishna's Pedagogy:

The Upanishads deal with the knowledge of the Self which is not a subject of study only, but of life. It is pointed out by the Philosophers that the Upanishadic preceptors adopted various methods while instructing their pupils. They were according to the necessities in terms of philosophical subtlety, developmental state of mind of the students and nature of the subjects.

- 1. Enigmatic Method:** A subject like philosophy which by nature is arid and dry was made interesting by adopting this method. Abstract ideas were made clear by pointing to a synthesis of opposites. The *Isavasyopanishad* introduced the Vidya and Avidya and the Sambhuti and Asambhuti triplets by taking recourse to this method (Gambhirananda,1957).

On 28th October,1882, a Brahmo devotee asked Sri Ramakrishna: "Sir, has God forms or has He none?"

Sri Ramakrishna replied, "No one can say with finality that God is only 'this' and nothing else. He is formless, and again He has forms." "Do you know what I mean? Think of Brahman, Existence-Knowledge-Bliss Absolute, as a shoreless ocean. Through the cooling influence, as it were, of the bhakta's love, the water has frozen at places into blocks of ice. In other words, God now and then assumes various forms for His lovers and reveals Himself to them as a Person. But with the rising of the sun of Knowledge, the blocks of ice melt. Then one doesn't feel any more that God is a Person, nor does one see God's forms. What He is cannot be described." (Nikhilananda,1942). Here the import of Sri Ramakrishna's teachings is God is with form, without form and at the same time become many more than the mentioned two and that gives us a classical example of Enigmatic Method.

On 22nd July 1883 Govinda, a devotee asked Sri Ramakrishna, "Revered sir,

why does the Divine Mother have a black complexion?"

Sri Ramakrishna said, "You see Her as black because you are far away from Her. Go near and you will find Her devoid of all colour. The water of a lake appears black from a distance. Go near and take the water in your hand, and you will see that it has no colour at all. Similarly, the sky looks blue from a distance. But look at the atmosphere near you; it has no colour. The nearer you come to God, the more you will realize that He has neither name nor form." (Nikhilananda, 1942).

This example leads one to the synthesis of opposites where Sri Ramakrishna distinctly applied Enigmatic Method.

2. **Aphoristic Methods:** When the philosophical ideas were put across in short pregnant sentences and the commentators had to strive hard while explaining them.

"It has the advantage of compressing all the material of thought in short pregnant sentences, while leaving the commentator to scratch his head as best as he may on the interpretation of them" (Ranade, 1926). The *Mandukyopanishad* is full of such sentences.

Many people were charmed upon hearing for the first time the great liberal message from Sri Ramakrishna: "All religions are true—as many faiths, so many paths." Some may object, saying that at least a partial version of this liberal message can be found among the rishis and religious teachers of the past. But if one

scrutinizes this matter thoroughly, one finds that those teachers used their intellects to reject some parts of each religious faith, extract the essence of each, and then somehow try to show a harmony among them. Although in the past, rishis, teachers, and avatars had taught people how to reach the goal by following a particular path, none of them had ever preached the message that one could reach the same goal through all the different spiritual paths.

Sri Ramakrishna, however, practised the *Sadhana* of each faith, without rejecting any part of it and with equal affection for each one, and thereby reached their respective goals. Thus, Sri Ramakrishna experienced a harmony of religious faiths that had never been experienced by any teacher in the past (Saradananda, 1909). Numerous religious schools belong to our society; they offer different ways to reach the same Supreme Goal. Goal is same but individuals take the way according to his test or choice. In the field of education there is a space of this concept for implication. In teacher-education there are different curriculum offered by different Universities of the States. All courses of studies are considered as different ways but goal is same i.e. to be full-fledged autonomous teacher with professional ethics candidly.

Sometimes in 1884, at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna was seated in his room surrounded by devotees. Naren was present. Various spiritual discussions went on. When the topic of the Vaishnava religion arose during the conversation, Sri Ramakrishna briefly explained the quintessence of that doctrine, saying: "This religion advises its followers to practise these three salient disciplines sincerely: love of God's name, compassion for all living beings, and service of devotees." As he said, "compassion

for all beings,” he suddenly went into Samadhi. After a while he came down to a semi ecstatic state and said: “Compassion for all beings? How foolish to speak of compassion! Human beings are as insignificant as worms crawling on the earth—and they are to show compassion to others? That’s absurd. It must not be compassion, but service to all. ‘*Shiva JnaneJivaSeva*’ - Recognize all as manifestations of God and serve them as such”(Saradananda,1909). ‘*Service to man is service to God indeed*’ has deep philosophical meaning. Sri Ramakrishna’s words shed a special light on the path of devotion. As long as an aspirant can’t see God in every being, it isn’t possible to attain true and supreme devotion. When true devotees serve human beings as Shiva or Narayana, they see God in others and are soon blessed with supreme devotion. After philosophical investigation we have come to learn that this little great message originally is the essence of the Practical Vedanta Philosophy.

‘*JabatBanchiTavatSikhi*’ – ‘as long as we live so long as we learn – is another example of Sri Ramakrishna’s using aphoristic method of teaching.

Using aphorism for imparting mass education has now been accepted as well prone method all over the country. Figures 1, 2 and 3 delineate that how the message of various governmental projects can well be communicated through aphoristic slogans as follows.

Figure No. 1

Figure No. 2

Figure No. 3

Figure 1 – (*SarvaSikshaAbhijan*) – *SobarSiksha, SobarUnnati* – Education for all, development for all.

Figure 2 – (*KanyashriPrakalpa*) – *Ami Kanyashri Kanya, Bhaviswateranannya*–I am the venerable virjin, who is to be treated as unique in the future.

Figure 3 – (*Rastriya Madhyamik SikshaAbhijan*) – *Pore Chalo, BarehChalo* – Go on continuing studying, go on continuing growing.

3. Etymological Method: It is used under the spell of Brahmanism. It has not affected in any way the formulation of thought. In the Chhandogyopanishad the word ‘*Svapiti*’ has been used which means ‘*Sata Sampanno Bhavati*’ or ‘*Svmapito Bhavati*’ i.e. becomes one with himself. The etymological method can alone help in increasing the vocabulary of the learner. In etymology the words are reduced to their basic components. The elements of a word are prefix, root, suffix, these elements are called morphene or morph. Some morphs change their meaning and form in particular words. To tackle this one has to learn ability to recognise new words and to avoid guessing their meaning. The etymological method has to be practised to increase our vocabulary.

Uddalaka Aruni said to his sons Svetaketu:

“Learn from me the true nature of sleep (*Svapana*). When a man sleeps here, then, my dear son, he becomes united with the True; he is gone to his own (Self). Therefore, they say, *Svapati*, he sleeps, because he is gone (*Apita*) to his own (*Sva*).” (Lokeswarananda, 1998).

On 5th August 1882, Sri Ramakrishna began to speak with Vidyasagar. “What is the significance of the Gita? It is what you find by repeating the word ten times. It is then reversed into ‘*tyagi*’, which means a person who has renounced everything for God. And the lesson of the Gita is: ‘O man, renounce everything and seek God alone’” (Nikhilananda, 1942).

Again in a similar circumstance Sri Ramakrishna said, “By repeating the word ‘*mora*’ (which means death) the word ‘Rama’ (holy name of Lord) reveals.”

Here teaching method is by practicing chanting and thinking of a particular word real idea of meaning is brought out as ‘*tat japa tat arthabhavanam*’. It is a process about drawing out which is already within the spell.

We have come to know that it is Etymological Method which was followed by the Sages of Upanishad. Particularly it is very much observed distinctly in Chhandogyopanishad and in the teaching method (pedagogy) of Sri Ramakrishna it has been reproduced.

4. Mythical Method: It was used for imparting a moral lesson. For example in the *Kanopanishad* the parable of *Indra* and the Damsel was used to convey the lesson of humility. At places the myths were also used to serve an

axiological purpose, for example, the myth of the Sun came out of the huge Worldly egg. It marked the course of the generation of the world system. In this method in using myth, manipulation is done to bring a continuous parallel between contemporary and antiquity.

On 25th June, 1884 at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna talked with Bhagabat Pundit. He said to pundit, “A hermit went to the ‘pious hunter’ at Benares. This hunter sold meat, but he also served his parents day and night as embodiments of God. The hermit said to himself in utter amazement: ‘Why, he is a butcher and a worldly man! How can he give me the knowledge of Brahman?’ But the hunter was a knower of Brahman and had acquired divine knowledge through the performance of his worldly duties. The hermit was illumined by the instruction of the ‘pious hunter’” (Nikhilananda, 1942).

And again on 19th September, 1884 Sri Ramakrishna was doing spiritual discourse with the devotees. He said, “When Draupadi’s clothes were being taken off, she cried earnestly, praying to God. God revealed Himself to her and said, ‘Try to remember whether you have ever made gift of a cloth to anyone. Then your modesty will be preserved.’ Draupadi replied: ‘Yes, I remember now. Once a rishi was taking his bath when his loin-cloth was carried away by the current. I tore off half my cloth and gave it to him.’ Thereupon the Lord said, ‘Then you have nothing to fear’” (Nikhilananda, 1942).

How mundane life transformed into spiritual life Sri Ramakrishna taught this, mentioning the above mythological character. Each person of the society is assigned to a task or responsibility. He who does this perfectly that is the expression

of humanity which is treated as human religion (*manab dharma*) indeed.

The core teaching of the mythological character Draupadi is, 'as your deed so your gain.' Sri Ramakrishna intended to mention here that God helped Draupadi because once she helped a helpless person. So always we should do such work which is good for others. This value education has become prominent when Sri Ramakrishna used this mythological character in an opposite way.

5. Analogical Method: Analogical method is a method of representing a phenomenon of the world, often called the "target system" by another, more understandable or analysable system. They are also called dynamical analogies. To explain the process of the apprehension of the Self *Yajnavalkya* used the analogy of the drum and the conch or the lute. Aruni used the analogy of juices which constitute honey. Again the rivers are merged into the ocean and become one.

On 4th June, 1883 Sri Ramakrishna offered to the devotees an analogy for a great lesson.

"One night a fisherman went into a garden and cast his net into the lake in order to steal some fish. The owner heard him and surrounded him with his servants. They brought lighted torches and began to search for him. In the meantime the fisherman smeared his body with ashes and sat under a tree, pretending to be a holy man. The owner and his men searched a great deal but could not find the thief. All they saw

was a holy man covered with ashes, meditating under a tree. The next day the news spread in the neighbourhood that a great sage was staying in the garden. People gathered there and saluted him with offerings of fruit, flowers, and sweets. Many also offered silver and copper coins. 'How strange!' thought the fisherman. 'I am not a genuine holy man, and still people show such devotion to me. I shall certainly realize God if I become a true sadhu. There is no doubt about it' (Nikhilananda, 1942).

By mentioning this analogy Sri Ramakrishna taught that "If a mere pretence of religious life can bring such spiritual awakening, you can imagine the effect of real *Sadhana*." If a person's behaviour is just and well, society pays obligation to him. Remembering this we should follow the correct way—the idea of be good and do good giving up the wrong-selfish attitude.

On 5th June 1883 at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna was telling the devotees about *jnani*'s waking state is no more real than the dream state. He told, "There was a farmer to whom an only son was born when he was rather advanced in age. As the child grew up, his parents became very fond of him. One day the farmer was working out in the fields, when a neighbour told him that his son was dangerously ill—indeed, at the point of death. Returning home he found the boy dead. His wife wept bitterly, but his own eyes remained dry. Sadly the wife said to her neighbours,

'Such a son has passed away, and he hasn't even one tear to shed!' After a long while the farmer said to his wife: 'Do you know why I am not crying? Last night I dreamt I had become a king, and the father of seven princes. These princes were beautiful as well as virtuous. They grew in stature and acquired wisdom and knowledge in the various arts. Suddenly I woke up. Now I have been wondering whether I should weep for those seven children or this one boy' (Nikhilananda,1942).

By explaining the relative truth and ultimate truth Sri Ramakrishna placed this analogy to Hazra. God is almighty, everything is under His will. This material world is relative truth and He alone is ultimate truth — it is the essence of this analogy. Thus to explain the process of truth unveiling Sri Ramakrishna used analogy (reasoning from parallel cases) and this analogical method was an important tool of his unique pedagogy.

- 6. Dialectic Method:** This method is employed in most of the Vedic and Non-Vedic Upanishads. The discussions among the teachers and the taught often took place in the Upanishads to explain the various *Vidyas*. The students raised questions and the teachers answered those questions. Occasionally, the dialogues could take the form of disputations as in the case of Yajnavalkya, in the court of Janaka. Yajnavalkya answered the six metaphysical questions, which were

suggested to him by the King *Janaka* (Ranganathananda,2005).

On 14th December 1882 Sri Ramakrishna asked to Vijay, "Why don't you come here now as frequently as before?"

Vijay: "Sir, I wish to very much, but I am not free. I have accepted work in the *Brahmo Samaj*."

Sri Ramakrishna: "It is 'lust and money' that binds man and robs him of his freedom. It is lust that creates the need for money. For lust one man becomes the slave of another, and so loses his freedom. Then he cannot act as he likes."

Vijay: "What must the bound soul's condition of mind be in order to achieve liberation?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "He can free himself from attachment of 'lust and money' if, by the grace of God, he cultivates a spirit of strong renunciation."

Vijay: "Don't the teachings of the *Brahmo Samaj* bring men salvation?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "How is it ever possible for one man to liberate another from the bondage of the world? God alone, can save men. The task of a religious teacher is indeed difficult. One cannot teach men without a direct command from God" (Nikhilananda,1942).

On 19th October, 1884 at Sinthi *Brahmo Samaj* Vijay asked to Sri Ramakrishna, "How, Sir, can one have the vision of the Primal Energy and attain

Brahmajnana, the Knowledge of the attribute less Brahman?”

Sri Ramakrishna, “Pray to Him with a yearning heart, and weep. That will purify your heart. You see the reflection of the sun in clear water. In the mirror of his ‘I-consciousness’ the devotee sees the form of the Primal Energy, Brahman with attributes. But the mirror must be wiped clean. One does not see the right reflection if there is any dirt on the mirror.”

Sri Ramakrishna continued, “As long as a man must see the Sun in the water of his ‘I-consciousness’ and has no other means of seeing It, as long as he has no means of seeing the real Sun except through Its reflection, so long is the reflected sun alone one hundred per cent real to him. As long as the ‘I’ is real, so long is the reflected sun real—one hundred per cent real. That reflected sun is nothing but the Primal Energy. If you seek *Brahmajnana*, the Knowledge of the attribute less Brahman, then proceed to the real Sun through Its reflection.” (Nikhilananda, 1942)

In this method the students raised questions and the teachers answered those questions. Through dialogues Sri Ramakrishna taught to Vijay the core Vedanta Philosophy. Here learner devotee Vijay had quest of knowledge and he asked questions on state of mind of bound soul, why he himself was not free, and why he could not attend to Sri Ramakrishna regularly? and about the real Self of human being.

Sri Ramakrishna answered through dialogue mentioning relevant examples and Vijay understood clear. In this dialectic method counsellor and learner both are active and elicit proper information.

Today’s most popular interactive process of learning is derived from this method which was applied by Sri Ramakrishna.

7. **Synthetic Method:** This is the method through which all the divergent ideas were expressed. No separation was made between the inner and the outer spheres. It was outwardly viewed that the heart was the central thing in the organism. The prana, too, was the most vital thing round which moved the whole system of corporeal existence. The Sun also occupied the Central place in the solar system, to them. What was inwardly the prana so was outwardly the Sun. (Gambhirananda, 1958) The Upanishadic preceptors introduced the three Vidyas viz. The *Dhara Vidya* which tried to plumb the depth of the heart, the *Udgitha Vidya* which sought to generate the reconciling rhythm of prana and the *Madhu Vidya* which explored the path of the immortal essence through the rays of the Sun. The six students in the Chhandogyopanisad asked cosmological questions and *Asvapati Kaikeya* satisfied them (Lokeswarananda, 1998).

On 15th June 1883 at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna had talked unceasingly to the devotees about real faith.

Sri Ramakrishna: "Once Vyasa was about to cross the Jamuna, when the gopis also arrived there, wishing to go to the other side. But no ferry-boat was in sight. They said to Vyasa, 'Revered sir, what shall we do now?' 'Don't worry', said Vyasa. 'I will take you across. But I am very hungry. Have you anything for me to eat?' The gopis had plenty of milk, cream, and butter with them. Vyasa ate it all. Then the gopis asked, 'Well, sir, what about crossing the river?' Vyasa stood on the bank of the Jamuna and said, 'O Jamuna, if I have not eaten anything today, then may your waters part so that we may all walk to the other side.' No sooner did the sage utter these words than the waters of the Jamuna parted. The gopis were speechless with wonder. 'He ate so much just now,' they said to themselves, 'and he says, "If I have not eaten anything.....!" Vyasa had the firm conviction that it was not himself, but the Narayana who dwelt in his heart, that had partaken of the food.'" (Nikhilananda, 1942)

This is the method through which all the divergent ideas were expressed. Here the doer does not feel that he is doing but the observers are seeing that he is doing. The person who has achieved the sense that his real identity is only soul and not the body-mind complex, can express this attitude. It is the state of mind of a *jnani*. Sri Ramakrishna mentioned that *Vyasadeva* gained staunch faith that God as pure-soul dwells within him, organs are just instruments of that soul

so he felt that he could not eat but it was taken by God who is within him. It is possible when the ego completely withers away and pure self appears as individual which is instrument in the hands of the operator (self/soul).

- 8. Monologic Method:** It is also known as the method of soliloquy. Having given the right answers to the students' questions, the preceptors themselves over hit in their exposition and lost themselves in a soliloquy in the midst of many. In the *Brihadaranyak Upanishad* Uddalaka Aruni asked Yajnavalkya to tell that thread by which this world and the other world, and all beings are strung together (Ranganathananda, 2005). Yajnavalkya replied that air was that thread by which this world and the other world, and all creatures were strung together. Then he also told who the puller was within. In doing so he poured out profusely. (Ranganathananda, 2005) Yajnavalkya further poured himself out in his conversation with Janaka on the immutable nature of the Atman. (Ranganathananda, 2005) Similarly Yama, when once he began to speak, spoke in a philosophical monologue. He over hit the bounds of the original questions.

"The truth is that in case of these Upanishadic Philosophers, it does not generally rain, but when it does rain, it pours profusely." (Ranade, 1926).

On 22nd October, 1882 at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna had said to Master, Rakhhal and Narendra,

“I had to practice each religion for a time—Hinduism, Islam, Christianity. Furthermore, I followed the paths of the Saktas, Vaishnavas, and Vedantists. I realized that there is only one God toward whom all are travelling; but the paths are different.” (Nikhilananda, 1942)

On 27th October, 1882 at Dakshineswar Sri Ramakrishna was in his room talking with Vijay and Haralal. Some disciples of Keshab entered. Sri Ramakrishna said: “To my Divine Mother I prayed only for pure love. I offered flowers at Her Lotus Feet and prayed to Her: ‘Mother, here is Thy virtue, here is Thy vice. Take them both and grant me only pure love for Thee. Here is Thy knowledge, here is Thy ignorance. Take them both and grant me only pure love for Thee. Here is Thy purity, here is Thy impurity. Take them both, Mother, and grant me only pure love for Thee. Here is Thy dharma, here is Thy adharma. Take them both, Mother, and grant me only pure love for Thee.’ (Nikhilananda, 1942)

By placing self-words Sri Ramakrishna taught the truth seekers. Here soliloquy itself is an important tool for teaching. Telling his own experience by soliloquy he became burning example of his teaching method.

In another episode we find that Sri Ramakrishna offered everything to the mother of the Universe except truth. Offering all material relative good and bad he exclusively wanted only pure love. His inspired soliloquy is itself

treated as direct teaching on renunciation and unconditional eternal love for God.

This is to bring to our notice that monologic teaching method of Upanishadic period was followed by Sri Ramakrishna as well as he restored the utility of the classical teaching methods.

- 9. Regressive Method:** In this method the answer of the previous question used to appear as a fresh question. Janaka asked Yajnavalkya what the light of man was. Yajnavalkya answered that it was the Sun. Janaka went behind answer after answer. In this way he carried him from the Sun to the Moon, from the Moon to the Fire etc. and lastly reached the Atman which existed behind them all. (Misra, 1979)

On 28th November 1883 Sri Ramakrishna arrived at JaygopalSen’s house. It was about seven o’clock in the evening. In the drawing room Jaygopal’s relatives and neighbours had gathered. One of the neighbours was eager to ask question about mundane and spiritual life.

Neighbour: “There are such obstacles, certainly. Besides, the children may be disobedient. There is no end of difficulties. Now, sir, what is the way?”

Sri Ramakrishna: “But still there is a way out. One should pray to God, going now and then into solitude, and make efforts to realize Him.”

Neighbour: “Must one leave home then?”

Sri Ramakrishna: "No, not altogether. Whenever you have leisure, go into solitude for a day or two. At that time don't have any relations with the outside world and don't hold any conversation with worldly people on worldly affairs. You must live either in solitude or in the company of holy men."

Neighbour: "How can one recognize a holy man?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "He who has surrendered his body, mind, and innermost self to God is surely a holy man. Furthermore, he serves all beings, knowing that God resides in everybody's heart. These, in general, are the signs of a holy man." (Nikhilananda, 1942) In this method the answer of the previous question used to appear as a fresh question.

Here a neighbour of Jaygopal Sen asked a series of questions. But every question rose from the immediate previous answer of Sri Ramakrishna. First question was about family life as hindrance to God-realization. Sri Ramakrishna advised him to live into solitude. Then the neighbour asked about the nature of solitude life. When Sri Ramakrishna replied to live into solitude for a few days with holy man, the neighbour also asked about holy man's identification.

10. Ad-hoc or Temporising Method:

The Upanishadic philosophers generally confined themselves only to the problems or the subjects which were immediately before them. Prajapati

gave only what his pupils needed.

On February, 1882 at Dakshineswar Mahendranath Gupta (M) asked to Sri Ramakrishna: "How, sir, may we fix our minds on God?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "Repeat God's name and sing His glories, and keep holy company; and now and then visit God's devotees and holy men."

Mahendranath: "How ought we to live in the world?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "Do all your duties, but keep your mind on God. Live with all—with wife and children, father and mother—and serve them. Treat them as if they were very dear to you, but know in your heart of hearts that they do not belong to you. The tortoise moves about in the water. But can you guess where her thoughts are? There on the bank, where her eggs are lying. Do all your duties in the world, but keep your mind on God." (Nikhilananda, 1942)

Mahendra: "Is it possible to see God?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "Yes, certainly. Living in solitude now and then, repeating God's name and singing, His glories, and discriminating between the Real and the unreal—these are the means to employ to see Him."

Mahendra: "Under what conditions does one see God?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "Cry to the Lord with an intensely yearning heart and you will certainly see Him. ..."
(Nikhilananda, 1942)

Girish Chandra Ghosh is an example of the transformation of life taught by Sri Ramakrishna. Sri Ramakrishna gave to Girish's life is epitomized in a conversation that took place between them on December 14, 1884:

Girish: "Please bless me, sir."

Sri Ramakrishna: "Have faith in the Divine Mother and you will attain everything."

Girish: "But I am a sinner."

Sri Ramakrishna: "The wretch who constantly harps on sin becomes a sinner. How can you say that? Suppose a light is brought into a room that has been dark a thousand years; does it illumine the room little by little, or all in a flash?" (Nikhilananda, 1942)

Girish: "I often ask myself, "Why bother about the theatre anymore?"

Sri Ramakrishna: "No, no! Let things be as they are. People will learn much from your plays." (Nikhilananda, 1942)

It is not possible for spiritual aspirants who are householders to give up everything. In the present age, Sri Ramakrishna has given a new teaching especially for householders: 'Let the boat be in water, but let there be no water in the boat; let an aspirant live in the world, but let there be no worldliness in him.' Sri Ramakrishna taught them this technique: 'Do all your duties, but keep your mind on God.'

Here we find that Mahendranath Gupta was really a truth-seeker. He had deep thrust for God realization. Sri

Ramakrishna taught him according to his needs. He candidly instructed him to live a few days staying away from household affairs and to cry to the Lord with an intensely yearning.

In the case of Girish Ch. Ghosh Sri Ramakrishna did not discourage him to do theatre rather encouraged by mentioning acting as a tool of mass education. Sri Ramakrishna directed Girish Ch. Ghosh to assimilate the ideals of the novel characters of the play - it would brought transformation in life.

The Upanishadic philosophers generally confined themselves only to the problems or the subjects which were immediately before them. Sri Ramakrishna followed this method. He stood for learner centric pedagogy while giving instructions to each one according to his needs. According to the classical Indian education system (Upanishadic period) this method is called as adhoc or temporising method.

Conclusion

This paper has dealt with the science of teaching (pedagogy) as was demonstrated by Sri Ramakrishna in the light of teaching techniques to be found during the Upanishadic period and has tried to shed critical reflection on those classical methods with reference to the teaching techniques of Sri Ramakrishna. But it does not mean that Sri Ramakrishna blindly borrowed those traditional methods from the Upanishads. He did never imitate them. On the contrary those techniques came on the lips and tongue of Sri Ramakrishna as spontaneously as swimming comes to fishes in the water. These

all came to him as a divine play but it happened according to the needs and aspirations of the learners and following the social approval. Though classical methods of teaching appeared to have embedded in Sri Ramakrishna's process of teachings, yet it has fundamentality, there lies the genius of Sri Ramakrishna as 'Lokasikshak' (mass teacher).

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